

APPG for Music Education

National Plan for Music Education

Dr Adam Whittaker, Royal Birmingham Conservatoire

adam.whittaker@bcu.ac.uk

Music Hubs, previously Music Education Hubs, come in many shapes and sizes, with different operational models and underpinning philosophies. These range from de-facto music services within a local authority, through to commissioning organisations who engage freelancers and local organisations to deliver musical activities across a geographical area. The new changes in geographical boundaries will see yet more different ways of working and potentially facilitate increased joining up of provision. But it isn't clear at this stage whether it will change the fact that the experience of children in one parliamentary constituency is likely to be significantly different from that in a neighbouring seat. This has an impact for every constituency in England. A question I want to lodge at the outset is how do we think about 'getting in' to music, and what does this mean for 'getting on' with it?

For several years I was a lead researcher on the national music education hub data return analysis, along with colleagues at Birmingham City University. These data tell us stories about the activities that were taking place and the positive impacts of these, but also about the complex relationships that music hubs were constantly negotiating.

The data showed that lots of young people were getting the chance to learn a musical instrument through Whole Class Ensemble Tuition, and that there were lots of ensembles being delivered within schools with the support of hubs, or run entirely by hubs. There were lots of ways to 'get in' to music. Against these common metrics, there were variations in offer depending on where you lived. In some Hub regions, ensembles are free of charge, in others they aren't. For some children, they will have whole class ensemble tuition for just a term free of charge. Others get a whole year. Some children get to take an instrument home, others are held exclusively in the school. A few get to use the instrument in the next year even after they have potentially stopped receiving tuition. Sometimes parents have to contribute to the costs of 'free' provision. In other cases they don't. It is worth saying that as I use the word 'free' here, I mean for the pupils as end users. I'm aware that someone is

paying for this somewhere. Larger geographic areas may address this in part but there are still going to be regional variations. All this has an impact on the extent to which someone can ‘get on’ with music.

Whilst local decision making is important, there may be tension between Music Hubs as umbrella organisations to support a wide range of music making opportunities in an area and as providers of traded services on sustainable financial footings. They are working in challenging school environments where music may be simultaneously celebrated and seen by some as an inconvenience, a ‘hobby’ or a distraction from ‘real learning’, or, more concerningly, as cheap PPA cover. We are foolish if we underestimate the impact this has on the ability for music to thrive in every school.

Forgive me as I now labour what seems a tedious point around delineating areas of activity. The National Plan is not interchangeable with the National Curriculum for Music. Similarly, the Model Music Curriculum is non-statutory guidance to enhance in-school musical delivery and is different from the National Plan. The National Plan covers a mixture of in and out of school provision, but its implementation is put, in part, on organisations separate from schools, which are all structured differently. The work of Music Hubs is to **support** and **enhance** the musical offer that should already be in place as a bare minimum until Key Stage 3. They are not, and never were, constituted to **deliver** that curriculum music entitlement in its entirety.

However, in response to almost any piece of news coverage or research about music education, official comments conflate provision that falls under the auspices of Music Hubs with those that take place specifically in school. For example, a recent article in the Guardian showed that there were decreasing numbers of GCSE entries; provisional figures have this at 11.8% lower in 2023 than the previous year, leaving around 30,000 entries in total. The Department for Education response read: “To encourage more young people to take up music we’re investing £79m per year in funding for the music hubs programme to 2025 and have published the National Plan for Music Education to ensure every young person has access to a high-quality music education. In addition, our music progression fund supports the most disadvantaged pupils with significant musical potential, enthusiasm and commitment.” To my mind, this kind of comment rather unhelpfully characterises the specific work that Music Hubs do **as** school-based music education, which is clearly closely

related, but operates differently. It could be interpreted as learning to play an instrument = music education. We know that, in practice, Music Hub activity in some schools **is** the totality of music provision. But if a school doesn't offer a music qualification in the first place, then how on earth can the child choose it. We need to monitor this thoughtfully and carefully if Music Hubs are to be judged fairly and school curricula properly considered.

A key part of the shift in emphasis in the refreshed National Plan is the focus on progression. We know that some music hubs are able to track progression over long spans of time, but not all can. There is also only a limited interface between the Hub work and what is going on in the unregulated spaces of private teaching and musical education spheres outside of formal contexts.

Music Hub data tells us that, pre-Covid at least, they were reaching increasing numbers of young people, a good thing I'm sure you'll agree. More young people are getting the chance to play a musical instrument and sing. Looking more closely at this though, the same data tells us that the number of advanced students is decreasing. In 2013/14, Hubs were working with 22,356 young musicians at advanced levels. In 2018/19, that was 19,849. Last year it was 11,163. This is in the context of Music Hubs working with nearly 200,000 more young people in 2018/19 compared with 2013/14.

Why might this be? Well, one possibility is that there are simply fewer young people continuing to play instruments to advanced levels. But, if there are fewer advanced musicians being reported in Music Hub data, could it also mean that these learners are simply getting their tuition and support elsewhere? If that's the case, it likely falls to personal and familial financial contribution to meet those costs. The national vocational qualifications data shows that there has been an increase in the numbers of entries at Grade 7 and 8 across all music performance exams, accounted for in part by the expansion of offerings across the sector. So, if we extend this a bit further, are we simply creating a system whereby a Music Hub can get you started but, if you're really serious about it, you'll have to look beyond that framework? Essentially, are we so busy thinking about 'getting in' that we're not always providing the routes to 'get on'. I'd like to think not, but it is a legitimate question.

APPG Music Education – July 2023 – AW contribution

I know the new National Plan progression fund is designed to support this. £25 million could support around 21,000 young people to have about 40 hours of tuition in one year, if we didn't pay a penny for a single instrument, nor incur any administrative costs in assessing need. A £2 million pilot would therefore be a start, but it isn't going to address some of the more fundamental challenges to progression. That said, there are some significant opportunities here, especially in terms of targeted support for underrepresented groups. But there is a real need to think carefully about how young people can move through different stages of learning within the National Plan framework. In economic terms, this will mean the greatest return on investment. In educational terms, this will give more young people a meaningful chance to develop a lifelong interest in participating in music.

Thus, it is important that we are cautious that the frameworks that are currently set out don't inadvertently entrench a two-tier system where efforts are concentrated at the earlier, likely free, stages of learning. What happens when a child wants to progress. Where are the progression routes and opportunities to broaden musical horizons? These might come in various forms and be supported within a school and/or beyond its walls, but this is contingent in part on schools being held to account on their musical offerings.

If the ambitious aims of the National Plan are to succeed then all aspects of the system to which it is directly connected must also hold music in the same place and prominence. Parliamentarians may wish to ask schools in their local area what is going on musically, how staff are supported to develop musically, and what the offer is right across their constituencies, especially outside of the main towns/cities. Thinking about longer-term coordination of multiple pathways, and the ability to move between these over a larger area, is key to allow children to progress meaningfully.